

Scientific article

Comparison of wind turbine load surrogate model performances with multi-scale local inflow parameterization

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Abstract: *Accurate and computationally efficient prediction of wind turbine fatigue loads is essential for load-constrained wind farm control and optimization. This work compares surrogate models trained using a hierarchy of local inflow parameterizations, ranging from rotor-averaged to sector-averaged, proper orthogonal decomposition, and convolutional neural networks, operating on rotor-resolved inflow fields. All models are trained on dynamic farm-level aero-servo-elastic simulations database and evaluated for predictive accuracy, wake-induced load sensitivity, and generalization to larger wind farm layouts. Across all cases, RA-based surrogates show the largest errors, while for the other parameterizations the error is within the seed-to-seed uncertainty. The higher-fidelity representations reliably capture partial- and full-wake effects. Coupling with engineering wake models is done via the newly developed wind-farm-loads python package, whose application reveals that a mismatch in wake-added turbulence between dynamic and steady-state wake models biases load predictions, highlighting the need for improved wake-added turbulence modeling and calibration in fast optimization workflows.*

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